

Research Article

Design of flexible reconfigurable patch antenna using fluid metal alloys and PDMS

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Abstract: Reconfiguration antenna and phase, there is a need for “reconfigurable antenna” in driven by various industries aviation, telemetric, satellite communication, etc...But above all wireless communication and defense surveillance lead the new trend.

With 5G in our meets a new wireless communication infrastructure requires very high radio frequency exceeding 20 GHz; at these frequencies radio waves start to behave like light beams.

They are most easily blocked by obstructing structures reflect on surfaces, etc...the results is none uniform coverage throughout the city making difficult for mobile device maintain good reception. The problem it even worse when mobile devices transmitting their signals back to the station because they tend to use low power transmitter when the signal is transmitted it might not make it to the receiving tower that also depend on where the mobile device is located.

A reconfigurable antenna can be made by putting small micro switches between elements of a complex antenna buy turning the switches on and off different part of the antenna are allow to radiate providing changes in the radiation pattern by quickly switching the antenna elements on and off the antenna move between several radiation pattern and find the one with better reception this makes it “smart”

Keywords: Design, antenna, PDMS, metal

Introduction

Almost everyone in a modernize country uses wireless internet on a daily basis. We use the internet to access information instantaneously. Some common uses of the internet include to checking email, shopping for merchandise, communicating with friends and family through social networking or instant messaging system, and keeping up with current news. Internet is an integral part of our daily lives. Because of this, we must develop a way to provide internet to as

many people as possible while reducing the cost. Developing a low cost high gain antenna can increase the wireless coverage.

We will start off by investigating Wi-Fi IEEE 802.11 by discussing the 2.4GHz and the 5GHz frequency band used for 802.11. This allows us to understand at the operating frequencies our antenna in order to comply with the 802.11 standard. Next we will discuss various types of antenna configurations and its characteristics. We will discuss the design parameters for each type of antenna describe and also define several antenna measurements to help determine how well our antenna is working.

IEEE 802.11

IEEE 802.11 is the current standard for wireless local area networks (WLAN). Most people refer to WLAN as Wi-Fi. 802.11 have four popular protocols: 802.11a, 802.11b, 802.11g, and 802.11n.

802.11b/g/n all operate at the 2.4GHz industrial, scientific and medical(ISM) band. 802.11a operates at the 5GHz while 802.11n operates at both 2.4GHz and 5GHz band. The 2.4GHz band is divided up into 14 channels which have bandwidth of 22MHz. Figure 1 illustrated the center frequency of each channel and how they overlap with each other.

Figure 1 2.4GHz Channel Frequency and Channel Overlap

To satisfy the requirements of present day remote correspondence advances, reconfigurable receiving wires, with their versatility and enhanced usefulness, have become an undeniably alluring component in future specialized gadgets. The reconfigurability highlight in reception apparatuses is commonly executed utilizing high-recurrence exchanging and other comparative procedures to change their recurrence of activity, its example, and polarization without incorporating various receiving wires inside a similar gadget. Regular reconfigurable receiving wires are commonly evolved utilizing profoundly conductive metals, for example, copper, which brings about exceptionally productive radio wires, however needs mechanical adaptability. Such

impediment diminishes the application scope of copper-based receiving wires to inflexible or marginally conformal have surfaces, contingent upon their thicknesses. Fluidic receiving wires, then again, receive the mechanical properties of the encasing material. The fluid conductors contained in fluidic channels permits it to take the state of these directs commonly encased in a substrate because of its low thickness [1]. Consequently, fluidic reception apparatuses can withstand mechanical misshapening, for example, bowing, extending, collapsing, and curving when utilized in adaptable substrates, and can come back to their unique shape because of its profoundly reversible nature [2].

A large portion of the customary receiving wires are created by drawing the copper cladding on the inflexible substrates to frame static conduit shapes. Such radio wires are profoundly effective yet experience the ill effects of irreversible structure misshapening and even harm when being bowed or extended past specific cutoff points [3]. As options, a few kinds of copper-covered polymer substrates, for example, Kapton, polyethylene terephthalate (PET), and polyethylene naphthalate (PEN) films have been examined to suit the need in adaptable applications, for example, radio wires. Like traditional substrates, the electrical properties of these substrates likewise debase after extreme bowing/extending, which thusly diminishes reception apparatus productivity. Another alternative is polymer-based materials, for example, polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS), which has been commonly utilized in mix with copper foils to acknowledge profoundly adaptable radio wires. Be that as it may, the semi-unbending copper foils may possibly experience the ill effects of irreversible misshapening after certain bowing cycles. On the other hand, fluid metals can be infused into microfluidic channels to manufacture profoundly adaptable and precisely stable receiving wires without trading off their electrical properties [4].

In [5], a more extensive survey of fluidics-based tuning techniques for the advancement of microwave parts was introduced. In spite of the fact that, this incorporated an audit of receiving wires dependent on dielectric/conductive liquids, it fundamentally secured adaptable and recurrence tunable radio wire/exhibits and needed profundity on polarization/design reconfigurability methods. Furthermore, conversation of late headways in best in class fluid metal applications was additionally absent in [5]. In [6], a smaller than normal audit of adaptable and stretchable reception apparatuses dependent on material materials was talked about. Here, the attention was on the advantages of conductive filler-based elastomers utilized in receiving

wires for bio-incorporated gadgets applications and the exchange off between radio wire stretchability and its presentation. Nonetheless, a point by point survey of materials, novel manufacture strategies, and assorted applications was not talked about in that work. In another work, fluid metals (LMs) and general strategies for creation of adaptable gadgets utilizing fluid metals were talked about [7]. This work concentrated on different LM designing and exemplification strategies, however needed profundity on receiving wire applications.

Materials in Liquid Metal Antennas

In antenna design, the available fluidic antenna materials can generally be classified into non-conductive, partially conductive, and conductive fluids. Non-conductive fluids include de-ionized (DI) water [8,9], ethyl acetate [10,11], acetone [12], and various oils such as mineral/transformer oil [13,14], which are used in dielectric resonator antennas (DRA). Partially conductive fluids like seawater [15,16] are also available and typically used in fabricating antennas for maritime applications, while solute concentrations in electrolytic solutions [17] can be used to fine-tune antenna performance. Finally, the third type, which this review focuses primarily on, is conductive fluids. Liquid conductive metals because of their solid-like oxide skin on the surface, impart mechanical stability to the elastomeric antennas and hence, provide flexibility while maintaining high conductivity suitable for antenna applications.

Generally, solid conductors such as copper exhibit excellent properties as an antenna's conductive element. However, their rigid nature limits their use for applications requiring flexibility. To overcome this, thin metallic films have been used for fabricating flexible electronics. However, such flexibility has its limits, as the excessive stretching/twisting will eventually result in micro cracks in these conductors, thus increasing risks of breakdown in flexible antenna applications. Embedded antennas within elastomers such as PDMS etc., may use thin metallic wires, which are capable of providing elasticity and satisfactory conductivity [18]. However, unnecessary design constraints (limitation of stencil dimensions used in patterning of PDMS + silver nanowire (AgNW) composite) along with fabrication complexity also make this approach unsuitable for low-cost flexible antennas.

On the other hand, fluidic materials by their very nature have no deformation limits, making them a suitable alternative to rigid or solid conductors for such applications. The lack of a fixed form and the physical properties of conductive fluids have enabled the development of a wide

variety of innovative methods and techniques to fabricate LM antennas. Even in cases where the radiative elements are formed on stiff substrates, the liquid nature of used LM materials provide additional degrees of freedom to achieve greater reconfigurability. The most popular approach is to fabricate LM antennas on soft and flexible substrates to realize elastic antenna designs. Such elasticity is not achievable when using solid radiative elements. A summary of the typical conductive fluids and associated substrates are depicted in [Figure 2](#) and discussed below.

Figure 2. Typical materials used in LM antenna design. Abbreviation: LM, liquid metals; PDMS, polydimethylsiloxane; PMMA, polymethyl methacrylate.

Photograph of a partially filled patch antenna taken as the liquid metal fills the antenna in a serpentine fashion to ensure uniform and complete filling of the patch geometry. (right) A close-up micrograph of the leading edge of the liquid.

Photograph of a complete, evenly filled patch antenna and ground plane. (left) A close-up micrograph of a representative region of the radiating element shows the PDMS posts and the evenly filled liquid metal.

Analysis and Simulation

Dipole and loop antennas composed of liquidmetal have been shown to have high overall efficiencies (90%) at microwave frequencies [1], [2] despite the relatively low conductivity of EGaIn (compared to copper) and the relatively high loss tangent of PDMS (compared to Teflon or Duroid). The measured radiation efficiencies for these antennas, however, cannot be extended readily to other classes of high-Q factor antennas, such as multi-layered microstrip patch antennas and telemetry coils in which electric field densities underneath or within the radiating structure are relatively high. The presence of additional material losses within the high electric field density regions of these structures reduces the radiation efficiency when compared to equivalent antennas that are fabricated using lower loss microwave materials, such as copper on Duroid or copper on alumina.

i.

ii.

Metal	Substrate	Radiation Efficiency	Reflection Coefficient
PEC	Lossless PDMS	-0.03 dB	-3.79 dB
PEC	PDMS with loss	-1.43 dB	-5.18 dB
EGaIn	Lossless PDMS	-1.38 dB	-5.09 dB
EGaIn	PDMS with loss	-2.40 dB	-6.56 dB

	Perfect	Solder	Extended
180	-8.4	-9.4	-7.4
170	-11.4	-6.1	-7.4
160	-9.4	-7.4	-8.4
150	-18.4	-15.4	-17.4
140	-3	-3.2	-3.7
130	-6.4	-4.8	-3.8
120	-0.7	-2.1	-5.4
110	9.3	9.6	8.2
100	12.8	13.2	12.34
90	13.2	12.9	12.7
80	2.7	6.2	5.9
70	-4.5	-7.6	-14.4
60	-0.7	-0.5	-2.2
50	-5.3	-6.5	-7.9
40	-8.8	-9.8	-10.2
30	-8.1	-8	-8.3
20	-9	-9	-8.5
10	-8.4	-9	-10.4
0	-10.4	-9.4	-9.4
Front to Back Ratio	14.2	14.5	14.1

Conclusion

We demonstrated a novel, multi-layer microstrip patch antenna composed of liquid metal that is mechanically flexible. Injecting the metal into a microchannel featuring a serpentine pathway of posts forced the metal into the shape of the microstrip patch, which is a low-aspect ratio,

rectangular geometry that is otherwise difficult to fill uniformly. The performance of the resulting flexible antennas did not vary significantly during flexing and showed no hysteretic behavior. Unlike previously published dipole and monopole antenna applications, the losses from the PDMS substrate and conductor losses can dominate for high-Q factor antenna applications.

Based on the results of this investigation, a multi-layer EGaIn/PDMS structure is achievable and may provide acceptable performance for many flexible and conformal antenna applications that require large surface areas of conductive materials (such as microstrip patch and aperture coupled slot antennas). Significant improvements to radiation efficiency can be realized by investigating alternative flexible substrates with improved loss tangents and alternative metal alloys with improved conductivity. In this application, we have presented microfluidic channels that are inherently planar (2D). More complex, 3D structures with interconnecting vias should be possible using this approach by carefully aligning multiple microfluidic channels.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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The graphic features a green globe with a plant growing from it, set against a background of radiating lines.

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